

EVALUATION OF SERVICE EFFICIENCY OF COMMUNICATION ENTERPRISES IN UZBEKISTAN

Turayev Shavkat Shuxratovich

Professor of Tashkent University of Information Technologies named after Muhammad al-Khorazmi (DSc)

Ibadullayev Sanjar Sodiqmuratovich

Independent researcher of Tashkent University of Information Technologies named after Muhammad al-Khorazmi

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13764258>

***Abstract.** In modern conditions, where telecommunications have played a decisive role in economic and social development, the quality of service becomes the main factor of the competitiveness of communication enterprises. Based on this, the purpose of the study is to analyze the efficiency of service delivery to communication enterprises of Uzbekistan, to identify the main problems and to offer solutions for its improvement. A literature review was conducted, information on service quality and customer satisfaction was studied, and a survey was conducted among consumers and employees of communication companies. The SWOT analysis of service to communication companies in Uzbekistan reveals the strengths and weaknesses of the industry.*

***Keywords:** communication companies, Uzbekistan, service efficiency, quality, customer satisfaction, recommendations.*

INTRODUCTION

In modern conditions, where telecommunications play a decisive role in economic and social development, the quality of service becomes the main factor of the competitiveness of communication enterprises. According to the results of January-September of this year, the level of coverage of the population of our country with mobile communication was 73.3 percent. 5 mobile communications in Uzbekistan operator is available. Beeline, Ucell, Mobiuz (UMS), Uzmobil companies work on the GSM standard, and Perfectum Mobile and Uzmobil work on the CDMA standard. At the same time, market leaders "Beeline", "Ucell" and "Uzmobil", which cover the network of mobile communication stations the most, are among the top three mobile communication operators operating in the Republic of Uzbekistan in terms of the number of subscribers.

These three communication operators make up 79.8% of all subscribers (individuals) provided with mobile communication. UZTELECOM is the leader in mobile internet speed in Uzbekistan. received the highest award in the nomination "fast mobile network speed".

These three communication operators make up 79.8% of all subscribers (individuals) provided with mobile communication. UZTELECOM is the leader in mobile internet speed in Uzbekistan. received the highest award in the nomination "fast mobile network speed".

The main purpose of the study:

It consists of analyzing the efficiency of service delivery to Uzbekistan communication enterprises, identifying the main problems and offering solutions for its improvement.

Research methods:

During the research, an analysis of existing literature was conducted, data on service quality and customer satisfaction were studied, and a survey was conducted among consumers and employees of communication enterprises.

The importance of improving service quality efficiency

Research shows that service levels are as important to consumers as products, services and prices. This applies to the world market in general, and to our country in particular. relevant. According to the results of an online survey conducted by the author on the Facebook social network, more than 35% of consumers of our country do not agree to cooperate with a communication company that provides poor quality service, no matter how economically convenient they are.

Let's put it more simply - imagine two buyers buying the same items from two suppliers:

The first customer had problems with the product. He contacted technical support and the problem was quickly resolved.

There were no difficulties in the second one. He consulted with the seller only once - when buying.

Q: Which one is more likely to become a loyal customer?

Market research has shown that the second buyer has a 13 percent chance of re-applying. And in the case of the first customer, despite the difficulties related to the order, the customer who is satisfied with the service in the return application has a 70% chance of becoming a loyal customer, because now the customer is not only familiar with the products, but also knows that he will get help if needed.

The quality of service has a significant impact on economic efficiency. An increase in the level of customer service leads to an improvement in the following indicators:

- Level of audience loyalty,
- Customer retention rate,
- Number of repeated appeals,
- Reputation of the company,
- Reputation - the flow of new customers by increasing attention,

However, an increase in sales does not always mean an increase in revenue. Improving the customer experience usually requires investment: expanding staff, providing financial incentives to employees, hiring contractors to improve logistics, technical support, and other services. It is important to reduce these costs to increase revenue.

Automation helps improve service levels without increasing budget. Many business processes can be automated:

- Receiving incoming applications,
- Technical support,
- Analysis of employee productivity,
- Collect contacts and feedback.
- Key tools to improve service:
 - Chatbots,
 - Virtual assistants,
 - Call recording and analysis devices and software.

Automation offers a wide range of opportunities to improve business processes. Technology is beneficial: By freeing up fixed and working capital, employees can focus on new projects and business development.

In addition, the use of smart assistants makes the company more attractive to the audience.

Find out how you can improve your customer experience and what automation tools are right for you.

Analysis of the effectiveness of services

Key indicators for analysis:

- Application fulfillment percentage,
- Response time,
- Contact cost - how much money the company spends on processing each contact,
- Communication volume for each operator.

The last metric shows how many calls are made through all communication channels for one operator per unit of time. The cost should be approximately the same for all employees and should be constant throughout the year.

Seasonal bursts reflect a surge in staffing. As a result, the level of service and the quality of service may decrease. When we notice explosions, it is necessary to think about strengthening the state or introducing automation during periods of high demand.

The simplest analysis of the service efficiency of communication companies in Uzbekistan is definitely an indicator of the growth of the number of customers. Let's analyze the statistical indicators in this regard. From 2015 to December 2023, the increase in the number of customers of the major communication companies in Uzbekistan, Beeline, Ucell, and Uzmobil, according to the results, has been a steady growth in the last 5 years. We can observe losses in the rest of Uzmobil's businesses. Not only these large companies, but also other communication companies in our country have not seen a big growth.

Diagram 1: The number of clients of telecommunications companies in Uzbekistan in 2015-

In order to analyze this situation, we will consider the SWOT analysis for communication enterprises of Uzbekistan:

Strengths

- 1 Population: Uzbekistan's population of over 36.5 million increases the demand for telecommunication services.
- 2 Young Population: The majority of the population is young and has a strong interest in technology and digital services.
- 3 Digital Uzbekistan: The "Digital Uzbekistan-2030" program is paying great attention to the development of the telecommunications sector by the state
- 4 Legislation and Policy: There are laws and policies aimed at developing the telecommunication infrastructure.
- 5 Foreign Investments: Foreign investments are being attracted to the telecommunications market, which allows for improvements in infrastructure and technology.
- 6 Technological Cooperation: Cooperation with large international companies accelerates technological development.
- 7 4G and 5G: 4G networks are widespread and 5G technology is being introduced.
- 8 Fiber Optic Internet: Expansion of broadband and fiber optic Internet services.

Weaknesses

- 9 Lack of Personnel: Qualified Professionals: Lack of sufficient qualified personnel in the field of telecommunications and IT.
- 10 Curriculum: Limited curriculum for technical and digital literacy.
- 11 Low Digital Literacy and Regional Disparities: Digital literacy and access to technology are low in rural areas.
- 12 Old Equipment: In some places, the technological infrastructure is outdated and out of date.
- 13 Need for Modernization: Systems need to be modernized and updated.
- 14 Service Prices: Relatively high prices of telecommunication services.
- 15 Expensive Tariffs: Expensiveness of some services and tariffs for customers.

Opportunities

- 16 5G Technology:
- 17 Faster Communications: Widespread adoption of 5G technology will provide high-speed and low-latency services.
- 18 New Markets: Access to new services and market segments through 5G technology.
- 19 Literacy Programs: Implement large-scale digital literacy programs.
- 20 Online Learning: Development of online learning platforms.
- 21 Technological Transfer: Implementation of new innovations and technological transfers through international cooperation.

- 22 Cooperation Projects: Implementation of cooperation projects with international companies.
- 23 Special Rates: Covering new market segments by offering special services and rates for small and medium businesses.
- 24 Business Digitization: Providing digital services to small and medium businesses.
- Threats
- 25 New Companies: The emergence of new companies in the telecommunications market increases competition.
- 26 Foreign Companies: Entry of foreign communication operators.
- 27 Cyber Attacks: Cyber Attacks and Information Security Threats.
- 28 Security Policy: The need for a strengthened cyber security policy.
- 29 Rapid Technological Change: Difficulties in adapting to rapid technological change.
- 30 Investment Requirements: The need to invest in new technologies.
- 31 Economic Stability: Economic uncertainties and fluctuations in exchange rates that affect investment and cost management.
- 32 Cost Management: The need for effective cost management in changing economic conditions.

This SWOT analysis helps to identify the internal and external factors for Uzbekistan's communication enterprises, so that enterprises can implement strategic planning and take appropriate measures to increase competitiveness.

Results

Based on the results of an online survey conducted with customers, as well as information provided by communication companies, the following results were confirmed.

In general, network speed in Uzbekistan meets international standards. However, the speed may be lower in some rural and remote areas. The network delay is also within the acceptable range. In order to evaluate the network speed of the communication companies in our country, the statistical data of the communication companies was used, according to which the number of 4G network users is 65% in Beeline, 75% in Ucell, and 65% in Mobiuz. if it did, the highest indicator was Uzmobile 88%.

Diagram 2 shows the usage of 4G network by customers of telecommunication companies in Uzbekistan

Regarding the level of customer satisfaction, most customers are satisfied with the speed and reliability of the Internet connection. However, some company customers have expressed opinions about network problems and slow response time of customer service. The number of failures and uptime are within acceptable limits.

Customer Service Response Time:

According to the results of the survey on the quality of service of communication companies, some customers express their opinion about difficulties in getting timely help and solving their problems. Beeline accounted for 68%, Ucell 65%, Mobiuz 70%, and Uzmobility accounted for 55%.

Diagram 3. The results returned by customers regarding the quality of service in communication companies in Uzbekistan

How to improve the quality of service of communication companies in Uzbekistan?

Before the question of improving the quality of service, we need to know what is included in the concept of quality service from the customer's point of view.

- Response speed - how quickly the company responded to the transaction;
- Efficiency-how long should I wait to solve the problem;
- Quality of service - whether the result is satisfactory;
- Is it possible to choose a channel for convenience, and under what conditions is technical support available;
- Opinion - opinion - whether the company takes into account the suggestions of users, how it responds to criticism.

Keeping the goal of service at a level that solves customer problems and anticipates their expectations. In this case, you must comply with all obligations specified in the sales offer or contract[2].

Increase service speed

About 30% of users will leave a connection if they don't get a response within 10 seconds. Therefore, in order to improve the quality of service, it is necessary to improve the efficiency of

processing appeals. The sooner you comment, the better. It is not necessary to hire the best operators for this: it is enough to connect a chatbot.

A chatbot is a program that communicates with users according to a certain algorithm. It's up to the business what to put in the script.

- Bot options:
- Advice on services,
- Send commercial offers;
- Notes, reminders about events,
- Answering frequently asked questions;
- Helping to order;
- Collect user contacts,;
- Conduct surveys,
- Transferring the dialogue to the operator;
- Principles of creating a bot

Build your chatbot from scratch based on your script or use pre-made templates

Creating and customizing a bot is not difficult and requires no programming skills. For example, SaluteBot can be assembled for free in an online visual builder. There are ready-made templates: from them you can understand the principle of the bot and improve the script by adding additional functions[3].

Benefits of Salutebot for business:

- 24/7 support,
- Response speed – 2 seconds,
- Processing 100% of incoming applications,
- Communication with unlimited users.

SaluteBot has been trained on millions of dialogues. It has the ability to analyze the messages of the User, understand their intentions and determine the need. This ability works to increase audience loyalty and improve service.

You can launch a chatbot in a messenger (Telegram, Viber), social networks (Vkontakte, Facebook, Instagram, Odnoklassniki), markets (OLX, AVTOELON) or on your website.

Customer Choice

Connect as many communication channels as possible. Not limited to phone lines and email. Give users the opportunity to communicate with you on social networks and messengers. But increasing the number of channels is only the first step. The second is to understand how to work with the program when information about the program is obtained from different sources. Manually maintaining the customer base is inconvenient and inefficient. Managers may enter information incorrectly or lose part of their customer history. If the operator works in several messengers, he may miss a notification in one of them and the request will remain unanswered.

Data integration should be automated to avoid losing customers. For example, using the jivo omnichannel platform.

Jivo collects requests from different channels into one dialog:

- Conversations on web pages,
- Social networks,
- Messengers.

With your Jivo account, you can send formulaic replies, use quick phrases and auto-suggestions. The operator can connect another employee to the conversation or transfer the request to him in general. Thus, the jivo chat platform increases the efficiency of operators and improves customer service.

Another advantage is the ability to monitor service quality for each channel and employee. The system keeps a complete history of dialogues, received and missed messages. Analyzing statistics in Jivo helps you identify growth points and understand how to improve your customer service.

Increasing the professionalism of the team

The level of positive customer sentiment depends on the professional qualities of your employees. Everything is important: how operators communicate, resolve conflicts, react to non-standard situations.

To assess the professionalism of the team, it is necessary to analyze the negotiations. If communication takes place in online channels, you can collect and learn statistics through jivo. But how do you control the level of service delivery when negotiations are conducted in person?

To do this, you can use the SmartBadge badge to record and analyze conversations with customers. A device with a voice recorder is attached to the employee's clothing:

- Recognizes dialogue,
- Cuts off external noises,
- Records two audio tracks: operator and customer speech.

SmartBadge provides speech materials in two formats: text and audio. Analyzing these records helps to assess the quality of advice and improve customer service.

Improve customer experience

Let's say all bugs are fixed, technical support is running smoothly, and customers leave only positive reviews. Can anything be improved? Yes: coding can anticipate and anticipate your audience's preferences[6].

New technologies can be introduced to gain an edge over competitors. Give users opportunities that others don't have. Providing exceptional customer experience is an example of this.

In general, the quality of service to communication companies in Uzbekistan is good. Network speed and latency meet international standards and customer satisfaction is high. However, there are areas for improvement in rural areas such as network reliability and timely customer service response.

Conclusion

In conclusion, the research confirms that improving the efficiency of services is an indispensable factor for the success of telecommunications enterprises of Uzbekistan. During the analysis, a number of problems hindering the development of the industry were identified, and concrete recommendations were made to solve them.

Realizing the importance of quality of service in today's competitive market, communication companies should focus on improving the skills of their employees, introducing uniform standards of service, and introducing new technologies. It is necessary to provide more complete and convenient information about tariffs and services, as well as to improve the quality of services. The implementation of these recommendations will allow telecommunication

companies to increase customer satisfaction, strengthen their position in the market and achieve sustainable development.

It should be emphasized that the continuous improvement of service quality should become a priority for all communication companies in Uzbekistan.

Only then can the industry successfully compete in the international arena and make a significant contribution to the economic and social development of the country.

REFERENCES

1. Matveeva I. V., Khomenko E. B. Institutionalization of information-analytical podderzhki malykh predpriyatiy: instruments and infrastructure // Vestnik IjGTU im. MT Kalashnikova. — 2015. — No. 3. — P. 39-42.
2. Abdullaev A.M., Kurpayanidi K.I. Predprinimatelstva v sisteme institutsionalnykh preobrazovaniy, subjects of the development of social-economic aspects functions with information // Novyy universitet. — 2014. — No. 2. — S. 55-60.
3. Arkhangel'skaya E. G. Osnovnye faktori razvitiya predprinimatelskoi deyatel'nosti i napravlenie gosudarstvennogo regulirovaniya va stimulirovaniya manogo biznesa va chastnogo predprinimatelstva v Republice Uzbekistan // Potentsial sovremennoy nauki. -2016 year. — No. 1. — S. 122.
4. Kurpayanidi K. I. Nekotorye problemy klassifikatsii institutionalnykh usloviy, opredelyayushchikh struktura predprinimatelstva v Uzbekistane // Aktualnye problemy humanitariannykh va esdastvennykh nauk. — 2016. — #2-3. — S. 44-48.
5. Shirinov S.E. Stimulirovaniye i podderzhka predprinimatelskoi deyatel'nosti v Republice Uzbekistan // Vestnik sovremennoy nauki. — 2016. — No. 3-1. — S. 119-121.
6. Kurpayanidi, KI, & Talibov, I. Sh., (2018). To the problem of activation of financial factors in the development of entrepreneurship in Uzbekistan. In International Scientific Review of Economics and Management (pp. 29-34).
7. Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan "O strateii deystviy po dalneyshemu razvitiyu Republici Uzbekistan" dated February 7, 2017 #UP-4947 // (sobranie zakonodatelstva republika Uzbekistan, 2017 g., #6, st.